

RELIGIOUS AND MORAL EDUCATION: ITS EFFECTS ON CHILD AND YOUTH

By

KOMOLAFE-JOHNSON, C. BUKOLA

*School of Basic and Remedial Studies
Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.*

Abstract

The view of this write-up is to provide a perspective on the religious and moral education on a Nigerian child and youth. In a corrupt society, where every aspect of it stinks with corruption, it is a necessity for religion and morality to be appreciated and demanded, in order to orientate ourselves and to inspire moral living on the great number of people in the society. In doing this, relevant books and journal articles were used. The findings show that the significance of religious and moral education on a Nigerian child and youth can not be over-emphasized. It is the concrete foundation on which the building of a society can be built. The nation is full of immorality which is reflected in many forms. The teaching of religious and moral education in our schools (secondary and tertiary institutions) will go a long way to correct all these decadences.

Introduction

The proposed partnership in this write-up is not exactly a blending of the two meanings of religious and moral education instead, is to bring elements of each of them into the partnership. In the source of the search for the materials for this work, it was discovered that there are good positions to adopt the best element of each meaning of religious and moral education. The term "religious education" can be traced back to the seventeenth century which denotes or often referred to as church education. The term came to have a very distinct meaning in the early decades of the twentieth century. A religious education could be looked at from two dimensions namely: (1) It could be an umbrella term for protestant Catholic-Jewish conversation

about education and (2) It could function as a bridge between religiously affiliated schools and the state (public) schools.

Lawal (2002) says that religious education are those processes designed to induct each new generation into the attitudes, belief as well as the practices of a religion or faith in order to promote the religion and at the same time provide for individual a unifying centre. Among the objectives of religious education are, to enable every student to know and perform his duties to his creator in particular and to his fellow human beings in general. Also, to enable the learners apply or use those religious teachings events, stories, experiences as well as approaches to solve personal problems, meet the challenges ahead or adapt to any new or strange situation. Lastly, to develop in the youths moral principles and values such as justice and fair play to humanity which are capable of bringing about tranquility and overall development in the society.

The term 'moral education' can be defined as the process of passing the generally accepted code of conduct 'of a given society from one generation to 'another. In other words, moral education is the transmission of right attitudes and behaviours which are acceptable to a given society to the younger generation in order to regulate their conduct in such a society. According to Adebayo (2004) Moral education has been spelt out as a process of enlightening the young people in a society about good and bad behaviours or characters, encouraging them to uphold good and discouraging them from bad so as to live a meaningful life worthy of emulations.

The development of religious education curricula has been a service to teachers. Religious education is a well-defined topic for the state-school curriculum, moral education is likely to be similarly defined as appropriate for classroom instruction. Education as a whole had a strongly moralizing character, the schools main work was thought to be properly amoral.

Partnership Between Religious and Moral Education

The relation of religious and moral education are two lifelong processes that get mixed together. Both tendencies have something of value to them, but to be consistent and effective, religious and moral education have to be conceived as having a negotiable relation within a lifelong and life-wide education. The overall

theme is that religious and moral education should be distinct but not separate areas, this principle can be accepted by both the devout Christian and the secular ethicist. In the world that has been shaped by Western enlightenment, an educational approach to morality cannot begin with religious premises. But those who act as if religion were either non-existent or morally negative just as stubborn of the religious fundamentalists they ridicule, it is time for a realignment of forces in battles over morality.

A lifelong framework for the relation of religious and moral education would have the following structure: (1) In early childhood moral and moral education together. The child does not distinguish these two realms and the adult teacher need not worry about the two processes overlapping. (2) Starting at about age five or six years, the young person needs to have some distinction between religious and moral education. This difference, brought out in school courses, may result in a sharp separation by the time of early childhood. (3) At whatever age the person finds an integral way of life, religious and moral education flow together as distinct but not separate elements in life. The person continues to learn, even in old age, from a dialogical partnership of morality and religion.

Religious and Moral Education: Its effects on a child.

According to Ridley Matt, a child is more ambiguous term than it is usually assumed to be. For example, the United Nations convention on the Rights of the Child defines a child as anyone under eighteen year old. However, in most contexts, to address a seventeen year old as a child would be insulting. At the other end of the age span, a child may not include infancy. When religious educationalists say that the church has been more concerned with children than adults, they are not usually thinking of early childhood. Education is a lifelong process that begins not later than birth. While most people pay lip service to this principle, journals of education and educational experts routinely speak as if real education begins at school age. This problem is especially severe in regard to both moral and religious education. The pre-school child does not have a religion; we do not hold the child morally responsible until the age of five or six.

If we link religious and moral education we might better recognize that the child's attitudes are largely determined before the age of six. The young child cannot exercise rational judgments and free decisions but the child's fundamental orientation is set by the care that he or she receives. Human rationality is certainly important to morality but is badly understood without the context of infancy and nonhumans. The dependency for childhood embodies a central characteristic of human life. Care comes before reason in human life, if we were to start with lifelong moral education and a moral education open to religious, we would recognize that care is needed for boys and girls men and women. Tronto says, that without care none of us would get through the first two weeks of life. The quality of that care throughout the early years stays with us for a life time. Morality and religion go together. Some theologians like Bernard Haring have even claimed that morality is inseparable from religions, Olatunde (2006)

Religious and Moral Education: Its Effects on Youth

Although a child needs to be given a religious and moral direction that is determined by a few adults, there inevitably comes a time in life when that approach is no longer sufficient. The young person begins to question the customs, habits and rules which were, previously accepted as the obvious way to live. Not so long ago this age of questioning and rebelling was identified with the teenage years. The adolescent (one becoming adult) was the teenager. It does no good simply to decry this attended adolescence, the positive side of this development is that young people have a longer time to come to an understanding , of their religious and moral lives. Adult may still fear the effect of foreign perspective on the young, but the diversity of religious belief and moral behaviour can be perceived as an advantage and an opportunity.

This period of extended adolescence is dominated by the school form of education. Moral and religious education find an appropriate place in the classroom. Each of them needs a name for the part of them that fits into the classroom curriculum, the preferred name for moral education is ethics. Ethics can mean the 'Practice of a way of life, as well as the philosophical and scientific study of such practices. In the twentieth century, ethics became the standard academic term. The

term religion has a parallel but more serious ambiguity, religion refers to the practice of a way of life, it can also be used for the study of those practices that are described as religious.

While the academic meaning of ethics (morality) is fairly easy to stipulate, there is often confusion and suspicion when one advocates putting religion into school that is, teaching religion in schools. Perhaps this tactic is necessary to get a place in the curriculum at all, but the awkward phrasing undercuts religion being taken as seriously as mathematics, biology or physics. As it is, religious education as the name of what is addressed in the classroom is more associated with driver education, physical education or drug education, that is, topics of questionable academic standing. In the early grades, religion would best be taught not as a separable subject but as a unit or units within other subjects probably by the time of secondary school, religion and ethics deserve their places as courses in the curriculum.

The interaction of both children and teenagers is central to the moral and religious education of every religious community. The opportunities for this interaction should be available so that the bond between children and youth can provide the rich intergenerational center in which younger adults can mature in their religious and moral lives.

Conclusion

Like religious education, moral education is a broad but ambiguous movement. Despite anti-religious bias among many writers on moral education, the discussion never gets very far from religion. People who would like secularization are always suspicious of moral education as surreptitiously religious. And indeed moral education is a place of convergence for religious groups. Where moral education is lacking is in having any strong academic component. While the schools and their teachers are constantly criticized for failing at moral education, a peace for moral instruction in the curriculum is seldom discussed. The school as a moral community is to provide control of moral behavior.

Being a complete way of life, religious and moral education is an inseparable component of a whole in the same way as politics, economy and other aspects of

human life. Mankind is in dire need of a moral overhauling. Religion is the mechanism with which this house cleaning exercise can be perfected.

Recommendations

Being a secular country, with no state religion, Nigeria is expected to have a neutral position regarding religious education in its schools. Schools have the right to either give religious education or do 'the opposite, religious education may be both Christian and Muslim at the same time in this case, and students divide when this happens.

Also, there should be an interaction' (s) between youth and adults, because this is central to the moral and religious education as this would provide a basis on which younger adults can mature in their religious and moral lives.

Again, parents should have the right to have specific schooling in their own faith and that Imams, Rabbis and priests should be invited to offer religious instruction to pupils in these schools.

Lastly, while the schools are given the task of moral education, school teachers should be very careful about indoctrination.

INTRODUCTION

It is obviously through display and library publicity that the libraries attract more users and project the image of libraries. If any library wants to achieve its aims and objectives for its existence, a lot of library activities have to be their functions. Given the definition of library by different researchers, it is a belief that setting up library is also a great challenge and can be made to benefit many generations. Library provides access to information materials and it is a place where information is shared which makes the society to move from one level of development to another.

Library have considerable experience dealing with different user which provides the role in supporting efficient library services. This is in providing a trusted services authority based upon librarians making choices, evaluating information as a par collection development and with a thorough understanding of what users need.

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